

Additive Manufacturing for Delta Robot Production

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Abstract—Additive Manufacturing (AM) has undergone extensive research, with its standout feature being design flexibility. This technological process is not merely an alternative to traditional methods but a tool that can change how parts can be produced. Structure can be made including monolithic and compliant mechanisms. Monolithic mechanisms offer immediate usability, saving time and cost, while compliant mechanisms replace joints with flexible elements for enhanced predictability and durability. The DeltaFlex robot, an illustrative example, combines monolithic design with compliant joints, showcasing its potential for precision applications. Its construction employs Design for Additive Manufacturing (DfAM) strategies, enhancing mechanical robustness and versatility in manufacturing. Performance assessments reveal DeltaFlex’s low stiffness, facilitating motion, and remarkable repeatability, making it promising for precision-critical applications.

Index Terms—additive manufacturing, robotics, compliant mechanisms, monolithic mechanisms

I. INTRODUCTION

Additive Manufacturing (AM) has been the subject of extensive research in recent decades, and one of its primary strengths is its design flexibility. It allows for the production of virtually any geometric shape. This characteristic has ushered in a new approach to manufacturing, where AM isn’t just seen as an alternative to traditional methods like milling and turning but rather as a tool that can fundamentally change how parts are produced. The freedom in design enables the production of elements that could be difficult to manufacture with traditional technological processes, such as *monolithic* and *compliant mechanisms*. Monolithic mechanisms [1] stand out due to their immediate usability once manufactured, resulting in significant time and cost savings and lightweight parts. Since there is no need to precisely mate parts, fabrication processes with looser tolerances (therefore more affordable) can be adopted. Compliant mechanisms replace joints with compliant elements such as flexure hinges or elastic bearings and function by transmitting motion through the deformation of a flexible component

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Fig. 1. Photograph of the DeltaFlex

[2]. In contrast to conventional kinematic pairs, compliant joints display a greater degree of predictability and durability owing to their immunity to wear, despite generally allowing lower ranges of motion. Parallel robots are particularly well-suited for implementations with flexible joints [3], given that the required range of motion for individual joints is often lesser than that required for serial architectures. In literature, examples of devices produced with AM that integrate both compliant and monolithic mechanisms can be found [4]. An illustrative example of a monolithic robot produced with AM and employing compliant joints is the DeltaFlex, presented in this abstract (Fig. 1).

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE SYSTEM

The architecture presented in this abstract involves the following features:

- it is monolithic and employs compliant joints; it, therefore, is characterised by all of the advantages presented before;
- it adopts delta kinematics [5], which is known for its light structure, high speed, and high accuracy, which make it suitable for applications such as packaging and pick-and-place operations [6];
- an additive manufacturing strategy, Design for Additive Manufacturing (DfAM), was implemented for the entire robot’s construction. In particular, each arm’s flexures were designed to grow orthogonally to a common orientation. This choice of build direction optimizes the mechanical robustness of every flexure. To minimize the necessity for support structures, horizontal geometric elements were gradually extended from the lateral surfaces at an inclination greater than 45° , making them inherently self-supporting. Furthermore, this design approach en-

Fig. 2. Different load configurations and reference configurations

ables the robot to be manufactured using various additive manufacturing technologies.

The DeltaFlex robot was produced using the Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) additive manufacturing technology. This was achieved using a 3D Systems ProX SLS 6100 machine, and the chosen construction material was Duraform PA. Duraform PA is a robust thermoplastic known as polyamide 12 or Nylon.

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The performances of the DeltaFlex have been evaluated in relationship with its precision and stiffness. The assessment of stiffness aimed at measuring the device's capability to withstand applied loads. The precision test was performed to assess the repeatability of the robot. The stiffness of the device was characterized with a *Zwick-Roell Z050* tensile/compression testing machine, equipped with a load cell rated for 50[kN] full-scale load (with Class 1 accuracy in the ISO 7500-1 standard). During the tests, the robot's base was kept fixed, while the end-effector was locked to the moving traverse. Both tangential and perpendicular loading with respect to the end-effector were tested. To assess the precision, the robot's end-effector was moved to six different reference configurations close to the limits of the robot's workspace for twenty repetitions. In each repetition, the final position of the end-effector was measured with a *TESA 01811001 SwissTast* micrometric dial gauge. The load configurations and the six reference positions are presented in the Fig. 2. The stiffness test findings are depicted in Figure 3.a) when subjected to loading perpendicular to the end-effector and in Figure 3.(b) under transverse loading conditions. The results of the repeatability test are shown in Fig.4. The plot shows how, for the four chosen configurations the average position shift is less than 30[mm], indicating good repeatability. The conducted tests offer an evaluation of the key attributes of the robot, emphasizing its reduced stiffness, which leads to minimal resistance to movement and enhanced repeatability. These findings suggest that the DeltaFlex exhibits potential for use in various applications demanding precision and accuracy.

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a)

b)

Fig. 3. Experimental results of the stiffness tests.a) Represents the force-displacement curve for the case of perpendicular loading. b) Represents the force-displacement curve for the case of tangential loading.

Fig. 4. Histograms of the repeatability errors and standard deviations for the six reference configurations.

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